

Gajkesari Yog

57 Comments / English Blogs / By Deepanshu Giri

Gajkesari yog is formed in a chart when Jupiter and Moon are in Kendra to each other and this has to be seen using the Moon as lagna, The effect of this we have discussed in one of the other blogs – [Jupiter-Moon Yogas – Lunar Astro Vedic Academy](#) but here in this article, I would like you to take a deeper understanding of this yog and how to remove any blemish to this yoga.

Moon is the natural ruler of the 4th house which not only represents our mother earth but the Moon is a representative of the earth, all our desires which we have in our life originate from the Moon and that is why the ruler of this direction is Kuber, who is a lord of wealth, There is a very strong reason why from starting of the human era, Money is an important factor in human life as even in astrology several yogas and quality of life revolve around the money.

North is ruled by Kuber and the Vehicle of Kuber is Nara which means humans, It is the desire of humans which keep everything on this earth moving, A human has many desires and these desires have no end but the quality of these desires can be controlled by the planet affecting the Moon, If

Jupiter is the planet which is Kendra to Moon, the desires of natives comes to an end and consciousness of native start emerging on a different level.

Jupiter is the ruler of the northeast and this direction is ruled by Shiva, who is in a superconscious state, the one who knows what is happening at any point in time as for Shiv time is not the entity, He knows the past, present and future and this is why he is sitting at one place and smiling.

Who is Kuber?

A thief who was running after stealing wealth and during pradosh kaal on trayodasi when he died by his head on Shivlingam- became lord of wealth- Kuber became Kuber due to Shiv, Shiv is the one who granted boon to Kuber for Lanka.

The time period of the North-east is between 4-5 am which is also called as Bramh-Muhurat- This is the magical time of the day when you can practice to rise your conscious levels and meditate, This meditation, I learned several years back from a saint to wake up, wash your feet and face with cold water and sit for meditation, The results will shock you as a there will be magical moments within few

days that you will be able to see what is going to happen in few minutes and this will happen many times and then you will move to next level as this is the only time period when every day you can break the space-time continuum and travel with the help of your consciousness to a far realm.

Planet Moon deity is Uma who is Shakti to Shiv, Who asks questions from Shiv as Shiv knows everything but it is only the questions of Uma due to which all the literature of Bhagwan Shiv has emerged, and when these two planets support each other in the chart, this combination does wonders as this combination provokes native to do bigger work in life and gives undying fame.

Moon rules the North direction and this is the time period of extreme darkness 1-3 am at night when you are in deep sleep, which also represents that in this life when you don't have a clue, Why you were born? What is your purpose? As most people waste time by continuing to live life without asking questions as they are so engrossed by Maya and the weight of Kuber on their shoulders, that they forget to even think about the purpose of their life.

Every Human has a debt of Kuber as a tax to live on this earth as he is a ruler of the north direction, When we visit Balaji temple to give the debt of Nidhipati, our life improves, If you remember my lecture on Jupiter in 7th house has a debt of Kuber and becomes the prisoner of wife, It is only the temple of Balaji when you visit and pray to Kuber, married life becomes good, as Jupiter is a ruler of NE while 7th house is ruled by Venus who is a ruler of SW, Just opposite to it, that is why the problem in married life happens.

Similarly, If you ever find Jupiter problems in your life, The best way to negate them will be to visit the temple of different deities and pray accordingly as this is not the scope of this article, I will stick to the Gaj Kesari Yog.

YOg Bhang and Remedies

As brilliant and beautiful as this particular Yog is but there are chances there is a blemish on this particular Yog and you might not get any effect of this particular yog at all, The reason is if Moon is heavily afflicted in the chart or Jupiter is afflicted in your chart and not in a powerful position, this yog might not fructify at all, As the shlok in Phaldeepika says, this combination should be aspected by benefics in the chart to give full results as this might not be possible in different charts, but same can be taken care of by using remedies as per individual chart as there are many traditional remedy and rituals, once native when try to perform gives at par results than any other remedy but remember this is a remedy of Jupiter and Moon – Shiv and Shakti which means results will come over a period of time in magnified forms which you might not have expected.

Let us look at an example by using Shree Ram's chart.

In this chart also, you see the combination of Jupiter and Moon is aspected by powerful Saturn giving it a blemish, also a natural malefic Mars is looking at this combination from the 7th house from the sign of Capricorn resulting in the Gaj Kesari yog should fail but let us see the exceptions now.

Originally Lanka was built by Vishwakarma for Bhagwan Shiv but taken as a boon by Kubera for all the yaksha to live in Lanka and then captured by Ravana, Shri Ram had to visit Lanka to fight Rava, both Shiv and Kuber are in lagna of the chart of Shri ram and heavily afflicted by Saturn and Mars showing fight.

Shri Ram before crossing the river prayed to Bhagwan Shiv by establishing the Shivlingam on the coast with the name of Rameshwaram, Think about this again why did only the south part of this country not anywhere else as Mars is in Capricorn which represents the south as well as Saturn is the lord of Capricorn South, He prayed to the god of ISHAN – North EAST- and specifically sang the famous chant of Rudraashtakm which starts from- NAMAMI SHAMI SHAN NIRVAN ROOPAM.

Which means- I bow in front of god who resides in North East.

Secondly, Shri Ram earlier directed Hanuman to bring the Shiv lingam from the mountains, which was the Shri Ram's way of pacifying the malefic effects of Mars as Hanumanji was late so Shri Ram did something very innovative, To build a Shiv Lingam out of Mud (Mars-Soil of South), pacifying the condition of Mars.

This was just before the battle with Ravana and he performed both remedies of Jupiter and Moon as Jupiter remedy by establishing a Shiv Lingam and Moon remedy by offering 108 blue flowers to Maa Durga and warding off negative effects, If gods were using Space and Time concept to ward off negative as this was a clear way to show, how to negate any yog bhang in the chart.

He had Saturn in 4th house so offered blue color lotus flowers to Maa Durga as a remedy as diety of Moon is Maa Durga and removed both afflictions to his chart.

In a particular chart, the combination of Jupiter and Moon was happening in Capricorn in the 12th house and the remedy advised was to keep Friday fasting as Saturn was in Libra in that chart when you think deeper why Friday fasting was advised and nothing else as a remedy, which actually worked very brilliantly in native's life- As the feedback of the native was that over a period of 6 months he has grown 6 times as I asked how 6 times, native said, I can see my employee size going from mere 15 to over 100 now in 6 months.

This is what people experience when the blemish to Gajkesari yog is removed by simple remedies, I am trying to cover the best of my articles, techniques and remedies via our quarterly magazine, This time I have written on how various people activated by their actions in life and what are the other traditional remedies with case studies of several people. Here is the link for the magazine

[Lunar Astro Magazine 2023 – All 4 Volumes – Lunar-Astro](#)

I would love your feedback and comments on this topic as this topic took me many days to complete and going through charts as this is part 1 of article rest will be in magazine of July.

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57 thoughts on “Gajkesari Yog”

GIRI KANSAL

16 JUNE 2023 AT 15:23

Namaste sir , sir i have moon Mercury Saturn Rahu in capricorn 2nd house and jupiter ketu in 8th house in cancer ...it means i have gajkesari yogpls only give me a remedy as i don't have any source of earning right now . . I m going to step into stock market ...sir , I will be thankful to you if you can give one remedy for stock market success

[Edit](#)[Reply](#)**NAMRATA**

16 JUNE 2023 AT 15:32

Well I think you don't have moon and Jupiter should be in one house

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